

STUDYING THE FIELD OF PSYCHOLOGY IS THE REQUIREMENT OF SOCIETY

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Abstract: In the article, in the current period of development of the society, every person should know psychology, be psychologically literate, the need to scientifically understand the laws of interdependence between the whole universe, man and his thinking, the main factor that ensures human creativity and the development of society. is said to be.

Key words: personality, system of social relations, formation of personality, human, religious belief and imagination, laws of interdependence between the universe, man and his thinking, intellectual development, scientific concepts,

Providing high-quality psychological services to the population, especially young people, coordinating the management of psychological services, raising the quality of cooperation between educational institutions and prevention inspectors and public representatives to a new level, developing a school of psychology and narrow specializations in higher education. in order to introduce the personnel training system and establish psychological centers:

firstly, although there are psychological personnel and organizations specializing in the diagnosis of the psychological condition of young people at all levels of the educational system, the lack of a single structure to coordinate and manage their activities affects the low level of effectiveness of psychological services;

secondly, although preventive inspectors and community representatives' service rooms have been established in educational institutions, the directions of their cooperation with educational institutions and the mechanisms for evaluating the effectiveness of their activities have not been determined;

thirdly, socio-psychological, including family problems in the society due to insufficient provision of psychological services to the population (divorces, family conflicts, parent-child relations, marriage between relatives, early childbirth), Subject to the negative effects of "mass culture", cases of suicide continue;

fourthly, the knowledge of practicing psychologists trained in the field of psychology in the higher education system remains general, and the practice of training specialists in a narrow field has not been established;

fifthly, due to the low number of admissions to master's and doctoral degrees in the field of psychology, there is a feeling of weakness in the formation of the national school of psychology;

sixthly, the financial incentives of psychologists, the unsatisfactory state of the activity of centers providing psychological services to the population do not give them the opportunity to attract experienced psychologists.

Although man is a product of natural development, his current state of intellectual development determines the current state of the development of society, the rapid improvement of science and technology, as a result of which nature and natural development are fundamentally changing. All this is a product of consciousness and thinking that is unique to a person. With the help of these mental elements, a person thinks about the reality that surrounds him and the laws in it, and determines the correctness, accuracy, truthfulness of the things and events that he reflects and remembers, or whether they correspond to reality or not. As a result, concepts, judgments and conclusions are formed in the human mind. This situation creates more complex thoughts, opinions, ideas, hypotheses and goals in a person. In fact, the thinking process characteristic of a person and his consciousness are formed and developed on the basis of such laws.

At the current stage of development of humanity, no matter how many advantages have arisen in people's life, lifestyle, education and work, it is necessary to recognize that various problems are also forming at the same time. Most of these problems are considered to be psychological problems due to their involvement in the education of young people, their life and activities.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's decision "On measures to radically improve the system of providing psychological services to the population and training personnel in the field of psychology" took into account the prospects of renewal, social and economic development, the needs of society, modern science, culture, technique and technology in our country. development and implementation of effective forms and methods of psychological services based on achievements;

development of effective mechanisms of youth education, psychological support in the spiritual development of a person, psychological support to create conditions for young people to choose an independent and conscious profession and form their personal professional plans;

to help talented young people to show their potential, to enrich their cognitive activities and interests, to provide them with psychological support

based on the creation of a psychological support system for the formation of universal ways of perceiving the world;

creation of a normative, material-technical and informational base that provides the required level and quality of psychological services to the population, including the provision of online psychological services;

carrying out research on the level of happiness of the population, health care, especially mental health, stress protection;

providing psychological services in emergency situations, developing and implementing training and rehabilitation programs aimed at supporting women who have fallen into difficult psychological situations in life;

assimilation and popularization of advanced experiences in the field of children's pre-school development, perception, consciousness and behavior, cognitive and social psychology;

systematic organization of psychological enlightenment and counseling activities, creation of its continuous methodical support;

development of personnel training in relevant areas such as medical and clinical psychology, psycholinguistics, psychogenetics, management psychology, commercial psychology, gerontopsychology, cross-cultural psychology, labor psychology, organizational psychology;

systematic preparation, publication and popularization of modern educational, scientific and popular literature in the field of psychology;

development of fundamental, applied research in such areas as youth psychology, psychophysiology, medical psychology, psychotherapy, pathopsychology, differential psychology, pedagogical psychology, psychodiagnostics, genetic psychology;

ensuring the effectiveness of scientific research in the field, developing fundamental, practical and innovative scientific research, forming scientific schools and strengthening the potential of personnel, widely involving young people in scientific activities, forming the innovative infrastructure of science;

thinks about the development of international cooperation in the field of psychology and the establishment of active cooperation with prestigious foreign higher education and scientific research organizations.

Accordingly, psychologists should pay special attention to the following: It is necessary to critically and scientifically analyze religious ideas about the birth of a person, the development of the human psyche, the laws of mental development, the main factors regulating mental development, conditions and norms. .In fact, we must understand that religion and all religious ideas or

religious beliefs are all expressions of human psychology. Concepts about the creation of the whole being, the universe and man formed during the historical development of mankind, the emergence of language, thinking and consciousness in a person, the system of mutual relations in society and its regular improvement and passing from generation to generation, about the vital life of a person, lifestyle and leaving the world is a set of imaginations. These ideas have been formed and refined over several hundred and even thousands of years, and these religious ideas and views have become indestructible or unchangeable in people of religious faith.

It would be appropriate to explain to future psychologists and other students by comparing their religious and scientific essence (valuation), without underestimating the educational value of religious images in the holy books. For this, it is necessary to determine the important socio-psychological directions for the correct implementation of youth education.

All advantages in human interaction, labor activity, industry organization and management are the product of human intelligence. Using the phone, computer, Internet, mass media - the advantages of receiving, processing, creating and communication systems in general, and the possibilities of their use, to justify the mutuality of the whole being, nature, society, man, his thinking and consciousness (understanding is necessary) possible

In spite of the above advantages and opportunities in the process of teaching psychology to students or in the course of psychology and training psychologists, we can see that there are some problems in their formation as psychologists:

1. Predominance of religious ideas in some students, lack of scientific basis in studying psychology is clearly expressed;
2. Inadequate scientific knowledge, inability to rely on scientific foundations in understanding existence is observed among students;
3. There are sharp differences between the knowledge given by the teacher and the imagination of some students (in the scientific or religious assessment of reality);
4. Differences between teacher-student thinking, understanding, and cognitive system, causing opposition and so on.

Such a situation goes back to family education, school education, shows that school education does not give young people enough knowledge of physics, biology, genetics, the history of the formation of the nation and society, social studies and other subjects, and is not connected with reality. This indicates that

there is a gap in the thinking and consciousness of young people. In their thinking, we can only see stereotyped expressions of non-scientific, religious and, at the same time, everyday ideas.

If a person does not understand his essence, if he does not understand the laws in the development of the human psyche, thinking, speech and consciousness - such young people or professionals do not know their place in the family, among people, in work teams and in social relations, as a result, they need to be corrected from an educational point of view. They make mistakes. It is no secret that such cases are felt in the following years.

If a person does not understand his essence, he does not understand his place in society, he cannot correctly assess himself, the people around him, and the interactions taking place in society. From birth to the end of his life, he makes mistakes and lives in a whirlpool of problems. He does not fully understand himself, his identity, the essence of humanity, and he cannot control his activities according to the norms accepted in society.

Why are laws, decisions, legal documents, regulations and norms developed, and the contents of these documents develop in harmony with the development of society? In fact, people ignore it a little. However, all these laws and regulations serve to ensure how the members of the society organize mutual relations and behave in the community. These laws regulate all members of society and the development of society, and serve to ensure the right path of development. Therefore, it is necessary to use large-scale oral and written tests at the entrance to study and at the stages of their professional training to acquire the specialty of psychology. Candidates who do not have a scientific imagination should not be admitted to the field of psychology, and students who have not developed a scientific imagination during their studies should be excluded from the ranks of students, because they cannot be trained as psychologists. It is necessary to apply this procedure at the stages of admission and preparation of students of other fields (depending on the nature of specialization).

Let's teach young people what they have and prevent them from aspiring to learn things that don't exist and are baseless. In particular, there are enough lectures, seminars, practical exercises, and independent assignments for each of the specialty subjects, but we observe that students are not learning as much as we expected. The main factors of this can be explained by the fact that some young people do not have a sufficient scientific understanding of the laws of the

universe, nature, man and his thoughts, as well as their predominance of religious beliefs and religious imaginations.

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